

ANALYSIS OF IRON MICROELEMENTS AMOUNT IN THE GRAIN OF ANCIENT WHEAT VARIETIES

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Today, a significant proportion of the world's population, including 60% of women of childbearing age and 56% of young children, have been diagnosed with anemia as a result of iron micronutrient deficiency.

ABSTRACT

The amount of microelement - iron, important for human health, has been screened in the grain of wheat varieties that have been planted in Uzbekistan for a long time. As a result of the screening, samples with a relatively high content of iron microelement were isolated, and research is being carried out on indicators such as cultivation technology, biochemical indicators and resistance to unfavorable factors in conditions of grassland alluvial soils of the Khorezm Oasis.

One of the main reasons for this is the lack of macro-and microelements necessary for the human body in the composition of food products obtained from cereal crops [4].

Iron is the most necessary resource for the human body, participates in complex physiological processes and performs the most important tasks. It is difficult to imagine a human organism without iron. It is contained in tissues, fluids in the body, micromolecular proteins that the eye does not progress, and performs the main, important functions in ensuring the participation of the cell membrane in biochemical processes, active participation in the respiration of cells and the norm of metabolism in tissues [1].

The human body contains about 4-5 grams (4000-5000 milligrams) of iron microelements. 56 percent of it is found in erythrocytes, 30 percent in the liver, spleen, bone marrow (as ferritin), 9 percent in muscles (as myoglobin), 1-2 percent in blood serum, 3-4 percent in the skin and other tissues [2].

A person's need for iron comes from his gender, age, body structure, etc. About 1-1.2 milligrams of iron per day is lost from the human body as a result of sweating, nail extraction, pus, feces, hair loss or removal. If 1-1.2 milligrams of iron are absorbed by the body with food and the role of the Lost is compensated, iron deficiency does not develop.

According to WHO, iron deficiency is the most common eating disorder in the world. Iron deficiency and its anemia affect more than 3.5 billion people in developing countries.

Iron deficiency anemia has become an urgent problem in the world over the past 20-25 years. Scientists have found that in iron deficiency anemia, enzymes contained in myelin - brain tissue cells are damaged (as long as iron is involved in its formation), as a result of which the development of neurons slows down, as a result of which children have a decrease in reading ability, memory, grow mentally weak. That is why the number of mentally retarded children around the world is increasing in the regions where this disease has become common in recent times [5].

That is why iron deficiency anemia, cases of iron deficiency in the body are not a simple medical problem, but a universal, original problem of our future generation and affect the socio-economic development of the country.

For several years in Uzbekistan, there have been attempts to enrich flour for the purpose of fighting anemia. The goal of the National Flour enrichment program is that vitamin and useful microelements, which are now lost in the grinding process in the mill, are added to Grade 1 flour. The reason why exactly the first grade of flour is chosen for enrichment is that in our country the population mainly eats the first grade of flour.

In several developing countries, artificial fortification of grain, i.e. enrichment with iron and zinc elements, has been established. But as a result of the cost of this process and the need for complex technical equipment, this method is becoming less effective.

The simplest and most effective method is biological fortification, that is, the search for biotypes with a high content of these elements, involving them in the selection process, producing varieties with high yields and quality that can accumulate more trace elements in the endosperm of grain.

And in order to bring this process to life, it will first be necessary to study the nature, physiology and genetics of the resistance of these varieties to unfavorable factors.

I.Sh. Djabbarov studied varietal populations of local old varieties to improve soft wheat varieties, the results obtained from which indicate the following. Interbreeding other district varieties with local varietal populations improves the character and qualities of soft summer wheat, which will be important in creating new soft wheat varieties. About the value of domestic varieties as an initial material for selection N.I. Vavilov mentioned: "Before starting practical selection, it is necessary to know the local assortment well. It is necessary that it acts as the initial material in the subsequent improvement of varieties".

Taking these into account, we also made a number of observations with the aim of studying the impact of growing conditions on the accumulation of nutrients in wheat grain.

As an object of the study, samples were used of soft wheat varieties that were previously planted in the mountainous districts of Uzbekistan, local and imported varieties that were fogged in the Republic, and new soft wheat varieties created by the selectionists of Uzbekistan.

Research methods: Bioecological, physiological, biochemical and statistical analysis. The amount of iron microelement contained in the grain was made in the "Instrumental neutron-activation" analysis style in the Department of analysis and informatization of the Nuclear Physics Institute of the Academy of sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In order to check the amount of iron microelement in the composition of flour products consumed by the population today, more than a hundred samples of flour products were collected from all regions and districts of the Republic. In this, along with all wheat varieties, flour products prepared under different conditions were also taken for analysis. All collected samples were analyzed centrally with the help of international organizations in CIMMIT and ICARDA.

The results of the analysis showed that in the Republic the average level of iron microelement in flour was 34 mg/kg, the maximum was 94, and the minimum was 9 mg/kg [6,7].

It is known that ancient wheat varieties have survived mainly in the hands of local residents, and no special selection work has been carried out on the germination and varietal characteristics of these varieties. As a result, many varieties are mixed. Expeditions to the mountainous and remote districts of the Jizzakh, Samarkand, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions of the Republic were organized in order to track these varieties, analyze their population status and clean them to a certain amount and allocate them to biotypes. As a result of Q&A work with the villagers, several varieties of wheat were selected. Spikes were collected from the fields where these varieties were growing. Up to 100-200 spikes were collected from each field, which were divided into groups by morphology [3].

When we analyzed the data obtained, it was seen that sometimes Qizil bug'doy, harvested from the mountainous regions of Surkhandarya, did not lose its variety despite the fact that the variety, sometimes called Boboki by the local name, is very ancient, the quality was observed to be very high.

A similar situation was observed in the Oq bug'doy variety, which was harvested from the mountainous districts of Kashkadarya and Jizzakh region. This variety also distinguished itself from other varieties in its purity and high quality. Many local varieties of varieties such as Sanzar, Muslimka, Qora qiltiq, Kal bug'doy have much lower varietals and in many cases are confused with fogged varieties. This condition is more common on farms that farm on lalmi fields.

In the artificial enrichment of wheat flour with trace elements, one of the main nutrient elements of the population of Uzbekistan, it was found that local wheat varieties planted in the Republic from time immemorial can be used as donors. But as a result of the lack of separate breeding of these varieties and no selective work was carried out, the once popular varieties were mixed with other commercial varieties and came to extinction. Saratov selection, which was very popular in the former Soviet era, was used as a donor in wheat varieties Khivinka, while Bukhara varieties have completely disappeared. In order to revive these varieties and return them to the local population, a nursery was established, consisting of ancient local wheat varieties. In establishing the nursery, 100 to 200 spikes were collected from each sample found, and samples were isolated by separate morphological analysis of each spike.

Isolated samples are currently planted in the grassland alluvial soils of the Khorezm Oasis, with continued research on such indicators as the technology of their cultivation, biochemical indicators and resistance to unfavorable factors.

References:

1. Абдуллаев Р.Б., Ходжаев Ш.А., Рузметова М.С. Распространенность экстрагенитальных заболеваний у женщин фертильного возраста проживающих в условиях экологического неблагополучия // Мед. ж. Узб. – Ташкент, 2000. – № 4. – С. 65 - 67.
2. Абдусаматова Н.Д. Новые аспекты лечения анемии у беременных.: Автореф. дис. канд. мед. наук. – Ташкент, 2000. – 19 с.
3. Аллоберганова З.Б., Усманов Р.М., Бабоев С.К., Хотамов Ш., Тиллаев Т.С., Умаралиев А.Т., Скрининг районированных и стародавних сортов пшеницы по содержанию микроэлементов железа и цинка в зерне и некоторые качественные показатели муки // Узбекский биологический журнал. спец. Выпуск, Ташкент, 2008. - 63 - 66 С.
4. Ibadullaev V.M., Alloberganova Z.B., Usmanov R.M., Ruzmetov A.X., Iste'moldagi un tarkibidagi temirni atom-absorbtsion aniqlash // Kimyo va kimyo - texnologiyaning dolzarb muammolari nomli Respublika ilmiy - amaliy anjumani, Urganch, 2011. 34 -35 b.
5. Петров В.Н. Физиология и патология обмена железа. - Л.: Наука, 1982. - 224 с.
6. Хотамов Ш., Тиллаев Т., Умаралиев А., Усманов Р., Бабоев С., Аллоберганова З., Ибрагимов В., "Stydy of element composition of cereals and food in various climate zones of Uzbekistan by activation analysis". // The fifth eurasian conference nukcear sciencevandbits application, Ankara, 2008. - 146 p.
7. O'zbekiston Davlat Standarti "Vitamin - mineral aralashmasi bilan boyitilgan novvoyxona bug'doy uni" boyitilgan unning sifatiga qo'yiladigan talablarni belgilab beruvchi davlat standarti. 11.04.2006.